

Local Government in Canada

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

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November 2021

The Country Report on Local Government in Canada is a product of the LoGov-project: “Local Government and the Changing Urban-Rural Interplay”.

The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 823961.

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People's Participation in Local Decision-Making

6.1. People’s Participation in Local Decision-Making in Canada: An Introduction

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Public participation in local politics and decision-making in Canadian municipalities is somewhat paradoxical. On the one hand, local government structures and processes are very open to public involvement at many stages of decision-making. On the other hand, participation of all kinds tends to be dominated by property owners, and electoral engagement tends to be low. These features of the participation system, which exist across both rural and urban municipalities, are to a significant extent a function of the particular structures of local government in Canada. In this introductory section, we will in turn examine both electoral and non-electoral public participation at the local level.

As in many other parts of the world, electoral participation at the local level in Canada is lower than at other levels of government. Indeed, a recent study found that average voter turnout in Canadian local elections in recent years was less than 37 per cent – compared to over 50 per cent in provincial elections and over 60 per cent in federal elections.⁷² As previously noted, most Canadian municipalities have non-partisan systems of political representation, the exception being many urban municipalities in Quebec, and a few large cities in British Columbia. Without the policy cues that might be provided to voters by the party affiliation of candidates, Canadian municipal elections are often – in policy terms at least – ‘low-information’ events in which most voters do not know much about the concrete positions of candidates, and tend to vote based on name recognition.⁷³ This in turn contributes to a remarkably high incumbency advantage. A recent study of a historical database of elections in four large urban municipalities found that incumbency increases the probability of an individual winning an election by more than 30 per cent.⁷⁴ Interestingly – and in contrast to the emphasis of the academic literature on incumbency cited above – some of the experts interviewed for this research noted that in the small town and rural context, the high frequency of incumbent re-election and even acclamation may be less a function of voter behaviour, and more a symptom of a lack of willing candidates for office. As one former civil servant put it: ‘There's quite a few places in rural Northern Ontario for example where, you know, people just aren't running. And they're even – they don't really have enough people to meet their quorum,

⁷² Sandra Breux, Jérôme Couture and Royce Koop, ‘Turnout in Local Elections: Evidence from Canadian Cities, 2004–2014’ (2017) 50 *Canadian Journal of Political Science* 699.

⁷³ Laura B Stephenson, R Michael McGregor and Aaron A Moore, ‘Sins of the Brother: Partisanship and Accountability in Toronto, 2014’ in Sandra Breux and Jérôme Couture (eds), *Accountability and Responsiveness at the Municipal Level: Views from Canada* (McGill-Queen's University Press 2018).

⁷⁴ Jack Lucas, ‘The Size and Sources of Municipal Incumbency Advantage in Canada’ (2021) 57 *Urban Affairs Review* 373, 373.

and sometimes it's people that don't want to do it anymore but they're doing it because they feel like they have to, so, you know, that's not good'.⁷⁵

Low overall electoral engagement notwithstanding, some residents – specifically, homeowners – are much more politically engaged at the local level than others. Not only do homeowners vote in local elections at a much greater rate than non-homeowners,⁷⁶ but they tend to dominate participation opportunities between elections. A growing academic literature on 'homevoters' in Canada and the United States largely attributes this owner-renter participation gap to homeowner motivation. Since owned housing is many families' greatest investment and local government decisions about land use have an obvious impact on the value of that investment; and since local government is largely funded by property taxes, which are paid directly by homeowners but not by renters; homeowners are more motivated than renters to participate in local politics.⁷⁷

In terms of non-electoral participation, Canadian local governments are quite open to participation opportunities in council decision processes. Not only are councils non-partisan, but they meet in public and provide regular opportunities for individual residents and delegations to present during proceedings. Such open proceedings have long been the norm in Canadian municipal government. They were reinforced by the so-called 'reform' movement of the early 1970s, when citizens' groups rose up against modernist planning and development initiatives, and they have become deeply entrenched in provincial legislation that structures municipal decision-making processes. In addition, provincial planning legislation in many provinces mandates extensive public consultation during planning, zoning and development permitting processes, a legacy of reforms enacted after a wave of protest against technocratic planning in the 1960s and early 1970s.⁷⁸ By contrast, instruments of direct democracy are very rare at the local level in Canada, and mechanisms of deliberative decision-making such as citizens' assemblies or participatory budgeting processes are likewise uncommon.

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⁷⁵ Interview with local government expert and consultant, Toronto (13 June 2021).

⁷⁶ Michael McGregor and Zachary Spicer, 'The Canadian Homevoter: Property Values and Municipal Politics in Canada' (2016) 38 *Journal of Urban Affairs* 123.

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This project has received funding from
the European Union's Horizon 2020 re-
search and innovation programme under
grant agreement No 823961.

